

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part XVI. Synthesis and Antibacterial Study of 1-Phenylcarboxamido-3,5-diaryl -4 (Substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) Pyrazoles

CHANDRA PRAKASH, G. C. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

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A number of 1-phenylcarboxamido-3,5-diaryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles have been prepared and screened *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by the cup-plate agar diffusion method for their antibacterial properties.

STUDY of antibacterial properties of pyrazoles¹⁻⁴, isoxazoles⁵, have resulted in the synthesis of several congeners and in continuation of our earlier work⁶⁻¹⁰, the present communication describes the synthesis of some pyrazole derivatives by incorporating a phenylcarboxamido group at position-1 in the hope that the resulting products may have higher antibacterial activity.

The intermediates, 1,3-diaryl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones were prepared by coupling 1,3-diarylpropane-1,3-diones with diazotised sulphonamide bases in presence of sodium acetate. These azo derivatives were later refluxed on a water bath for several hours with 4-phenylsemicarbazide in presence of glacial acetic acid to furnish 1-phenylcarboxamido-3,5-diaryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles. These were crystallised either from glacial acetic acid or glacial acetic acid-ethanol mixture; the homogeneity and purity of these compounds was checked through TLC and characterization made by elemental analysis.

All these pyrazole derivatives were later screened *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* employing cup-plate agar diffusion method for their antibacterial properties.

Experimental

1,3-Diaryl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones required for this work were prepared by the method already reported earlier⁹.

Synthesis of 1-Phenylcarboxamido-3,5-diaryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) pyrazoles.

To a hot solution of 1,3-diaryl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1,3-dione (0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml)-glacial acetic acid (1 ml) mixture was added an aqueous solution of 4-phenylsemicarbazide (0.011 mole), the contents shaken well, refluxed on a water bath for 6-8 hrs and left overnight at room temperature. The coloured solid which separated out was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid or glacial acetic acid-ethanol mixture.

TABLE-1. PHENYL CARBOXAMIDO-3,5-DIARYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	coli
$R_1 = p\text{-CH}_3; R_2 = \text{H}$							
1.	(A)	227-8	YP	80	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
2.	(B)	209	DYP	73	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
3.	(C)	225	YP	81	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
4.	(D)	232-3	OP	82	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
5.	(E)	236	OP	74	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	+	—
6.	(F)	206-7	YP	74	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
7.	(G)	239-40	OP	72	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
$R_1 = p\text{-OCH}_3; R_2 = \text{H}$							
8.	(A)	185	OP	70	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
9.	(B)	179	OP	65	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
10.	(C)	234	DOP	65	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
11.	(D)	238	RP	68	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
12.	(E)	193	DRP	70	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_5\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
13.	(H)	231	Lt OP	73	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	—	+
					$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_5\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
$R_1 = p\text{-CH}_3; R_2 = p\text{-OCH}_3$							
14.	(A)	254	OP	65	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
15.	(B)	143	OP	68	$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	++
16.	(C)	225	YP	63	$\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
17.	(D)	204	YP	65	$\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_5\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
18.	(E)	221	DYP	68	$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	—	—
19.	(H)	239	Lt OP	65	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_5\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
					$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_5\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
$R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = p\text{-Cl}$							
20.	(B)	198	OP	75	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	—	+
21.	(C)	228	DYP	69	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	—	+
22.	(D)	216-7	Lt OP	65	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	+	+
23.	(E)	231	DYP	74	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}_2$	—	+
24.	(F)	236-7	YP	68	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}_2$	—	—
25.	(H)	209	Lt OP	77	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	—	—
$R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = p\text{-Br}$							
26.	(B)	211-2	OP	68	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Br}$	—	+
27.	(D)	236	YP	70	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Br}$	—	+
28.	(E)	214	OP	73	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Br}\text{Cl}$	—	—
29.	(H)	225	OP	75	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Br}$	—	—
$R_1 = \text{H}; R_2 = p\text{-Ph}$							
30.	(A)	229	DOP	70	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	—
31.	(C)	204-5	OP	68	$\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}$	—	+
32.	(D)	216	YP	65	$\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}$	+	+
33.	(E)	235	OP	65	$\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	+	+
34.	(I)	238-9	DYP	68	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_3\text{N}_6\text{S}$	+	+
$R_1 = m\text{-NO}_2; R_2 = \text{H}$							
35.	(A)	116-7	DOP	64	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_3\text{N}_7\text{S}$	+	+
36.	(B)	189-90	OP	68	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_4\text{N}_7\text{S}$	+	+
37.	(C)	226-7	Lt OP	71	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_5\text{N}_7\text{S}$	+	+
38.	(D)	212	DOP	70	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_5\text{N}_7\text{S}$	+	+
39.	(H)	215	Lt YP	66	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_5\text{N}_7\text{S}$	+	+
$R_1 \text{ (or } R_2) = p\text{-OCH}_3; R_2 \text{ (or } R_1) = p\text{-Cl}$							
40.	(A)	219	BP	70	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	—	—
41.	(B)	223	DYP	68	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	—	+
42.	(C)	153	OP	70	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	+	—
43.	(E)	149	OP	70	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}_2$	+	+
44.	(G)	227	OP	68	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}_2$	—	—
45.	(H)	232	DOP	70	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_5\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Cl}$	—	—
$R_1 \text{ (or } R_2) = p\text{-OCH}_3; R_2 \text{ (or } R_1) = p\text{-Br}$							
46.	(A)	139-40	DPY	67	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Br}$	+	+
47.	(C)	169-70	Lt OP	75	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_5\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Br}$	+	++
48.	(H)	164	YP	73	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_5\text{N}_6\text{S}\text{Br}$	++	—

A = H; B = phenyl; C = *p*-methylphenyl; D = *p*-methoxyphenyl; E = *p*-chlorophenyl; F = Pyrimidyl;
 G = 4,6-dimethylpyrimidyl; H = acetyl
 B = Brown; D = Dark; Lt. = Light; O = Orange; P = Plates; R = Red.
 There was good agreement between C, H found and required.

The results of the biological assay indicate that the pyrazole derivatives exhibit mixed activity. On comparison of these with those obtained earlier^{9,10-12} it is clear that the introduction of a heavier moiety at position-1 of the pyrazole ring causes a decrease in activity thereby lending support to our earlier observations⁷.

All the synthesised products and their results of screening are entered in the table.

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